

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF THE
FORMATION OF A HIGH SPIRITUAL PERSON

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“Spirituality is not a gift of destiny. For spirituality to be perfected in the human heart he is heartbroken and conscientious, must work with mind and hand ”

(The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan IA Karimov)

Annotation: *This article is a scientific study of the important factors of education in the formation of personality.*

Keywords: *education spirituality homeland ideology morality Independence Development*

Subject, purpose, tasks and essence of the subject "Actual problems of education".

A problem (Arabic: Mysterious, mysterious; difficult to understand; blind) is a problem that has not been solved in existing knowledge and the solution is unknown [1]. Problem-solving and problem-solving require moving beyond existing knowledge and finding new ways and means to solve it. The nature of the issues to be discussed and discussed will be determined by practical activities and the need for knowledge. According to the famous German philosopher W. Geisenberg, the right question is more than half of the solution to the problem. It is not enough to have a clear idea of the problem. To do this, you need to know in advance the different ways and means of solving the problem. Each problem is solved using a specific theory.

Nowadays, the struggle for the human heart and mind is more intense than ever:

- changes in the ideological landscape of the world;
- Harmonization of geopolitical goals and ideological policies;
- The growing importance of ideological principles in the countries that have gained independence is reflected in the system of globalization of ideological processes.

One of the most important tasks of our time after gaining independence is to bring up a new generation of thinkers who will adapt to these processes.

It is a modern requirement to bring up a generation that is loyal to the motherland, devoted to its people, has its own independent opinion, is able to solve any problem consciously and responsibly, is inquisitive, innovative and loyal to the ideas of national independence.

Education (Arabic: Development, care) is a process that serves the transmission of intergenerational socio-historical and life experiences [1]. Education is a process of purposeful formation of personality. In pedagogical activity, the ultimate goal of educators and trainees is

a specially organized, managed and controlled interaction, which is the formation of a person needed and useful to society.

Based on the research conducted so far, education:

- in the general philosophical sense - the adaptation of man to the conditions of life;
- In the social sense - as the transmission of life and behavioral experiences of the older generation to the younger generation;
- In the broad pedagogical sense - as a systematic, specially organized, managed influence of the team of educators on the consciousness, behavior and will of students in educational institutions;
- in a broad pedagogical sense - as a process and result of all human influences;
- in the narrow pedagogical sense - as a systematic, specially organized, controlled influence of the team of educators on the consciousness, behavior and will of students in educational institutions;
- in a practical sense - as a process and outcome of educational activities of educators, coaches, leaders, group leaders to address specific educational issues.

The effectiveness of social reforms in a society depends on the morale of its citizens. Therefore, in the first years of independence, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan IA Karimov clearly defined the spiritual and moral foundations of the development of society. These are:

- commitment to universal values;
- strengthening and developing the spiritual heritage of our people;
- free expression of one's potential;
- patriotism.

After all, the development of a society requires not only its economic development, but also its spiritual growth.

The basis of spiritual and moral education is advanced national, spiritual and moral values, the ideas of folk pedagogy.

Spirituality is an internal positive, spiritual factor that determines the strength, development, opportunities and prospects of an individual, people, state and society.

Spirituality (Arabic "spirituality" - a set of meanings) is a set of philosophical, legal, scientific, artistic, moral, religious ideas, concepts and ideas that have a positive impact on social development.

Culture is a system of material and spiritual wealth that is acquired through human activity during social development and serves to meet their social needs.

Enlightenment is a system of activities aimed at inculcating in the minds of individuals scientific knowledge, ethics and legal norms governing social relations, improving education, studying and promoting national heritage and universal values.

Ideology (Arabic "ideology" - a system of views and beliefs, a set) - a set of specific political, legal, moral, religious, artistic, philosophical, scientific views in society, as well as spiritual and moral development, enlightenment and educational work. a system of ideas that ensures the development of the country and plays a leading role in determining their goals and directions.

Emphasizing the main task of ensuring a positive solution in the field of spirituality, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan IA Karimov said: "Our main task in this area is to restore our national values, self-awareness, national It is to consistently continue the noble deeds we started during the years of independence, such as the formation of ideas and ideology, the restoration of the place and respect of our sacred religion in our spiritual life, to raise them to a new level and strengthen their effectiveness. ... The ultimate goal of our work in this area is to form a strong, strong-willed, free civil spirit. That is, to bring up a perfect person who has an independent outlook, who lives on the invaluable heritage of our ancestors and modern thinking - a perfect person. " A person who knows and obeys the laws of his country and can be proud of his country. A person who preserves the riches of his homeland, enriches it and enjoys its beauty. He is a man who fights against any harmful vices and carefully preserves national and universal values.

Morality, on the other hand, represents the content of a person's actions, behavior, lifestyle, principles of life, rules, social relations.

Morality as a social phenomenon has a special place in the spiritual life of society.

"Morality" (Latin - behavior) is a form of social consciousness, a set of rules governing social relations and personal behavior.

Morality is an integral part of spirituality, the highest stage of personal development. After all, without morality, moral maturity, which is a measure of a person's spiritual and physical maturity, cannot be achieved. That is why in spiritual and moral education, membership and connection have a dialectical character and are important in the spiritual and moral formation of the individual.

Spiritual and moral education and the requirements for it are appropriate and systematic influences on the minds, feelings and behavior of students in order to form moral qualities in accordance with certain socio-ethical requirements in this society.

The tasks of spiritual and moral education are:

1. Formation of spiritual and moral consciousness in students.
2. To cultivate and develop in them spiritual and moral feelings.
3. To develop students' spiritual and moral skills and habits.

In short, spirituality is inextricably linked. Because a spiritual person is a person who is educated, moral, and educated. Therefore, everyone, regardless of age, should always be spiritual, educated and mature. Because an educated person is never inferior anywhere

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